

FACTORS INFLUENCING USAGE OF MOBILE COMMERCE AMONG SRI LANKAN UNDERGRADUATES

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Introduction

Background of the Research Study

Commerce is one of the areas that tend to substantially benefit from the growth of internet technologies. Indeed, commerce has changed from the traditional way of buying and selling to launching online transactions from browsers and lately, hand held mobile devices. As a result, the change is from commerce to e-commerce and now to M-commerce.

M-commerce, which stands for mobile commerce, is characterized as the purchasing and sale of goods and services via wireless handheld devices such as cell phones and personal digital assistants (PDAs) (Panneerselvam, 2013). Therefore, e-commerce transactions conducted via mobile devices (e.g., cell phones, handheld or palm-sized computers, and even vehicle mounted interfaces) using wireless telecommunications networks and other wired e-commerce technologies are referred to as mobile commerce (M-commerce). Today, a new business service model, that is, M-commerce, is growing quickly on a global scale. It has become popular due to the increased use of handheld devices, fast internet connections and the ability to connect people to various geographical locations. (Tamizhkumaran *et al.*, 2016).

The objectives of this study are to find the factors of M-commerce usage and to find out the relationship between those factors for undergraduates of the Faculty of Management Studies and Commerce of University of Sri Jayewardenepura. When it is considered about the Sri Lankan context, people use different kinds of mobile commerce tools to satisfy different

kinds of objectives. There is a trend of increasing the usage of M-commerce day by day specially among the young generation. Through this study it is going to strategize and reconstruct their attitude regarding the use of M-commerce. It will also help people further to identify the exciting opportunities mobile commerce add to human and how they affect and usage to the Sri Lankan university students' life. University students are among the highest digitally literate community in the country, and their attitude towards using mobile commerce is significant not only for businesses, but also for policy makers, decision makers, and academia as well.

Problem Statement

This study aimed at using the existing literature, the researchers of this study looked at what are the factors that influence on usage of mobile commerce and developing and state-of-the-art technology means that it is the ideal time for the m-commerce and business environment. With the rapid growth of the 4 G network and the growing number of mobile users, millions of people are using mobile apps and making mobile transactions around the world every day (Tran, 2019).

M-commerce offers its users various benefits and opportunities, including communication, goods transactions, services and information. Many of the M-Commerce studies conducted in Malaysia include information-based activities rather than transaction-based factors affecting the use of M-Commerce-based activities (Barry, Jan & Islamic, 2018).

Many studies have been conducted all around the world and these studies are about the usage of mobile commerce in many areas. However, few researchers have done researches about usage of mobile commerce. According to the literature review, it is found that each researcher had only considered about their local context. In Sri Lankan context, it is very difficult to find research which are carried out in relation to mobile commerce usage. Though we find number of research articles all around the world on this area, there is only very limited number of research found

in Sri Lanka on this topic. Accordingly, this study tries to fill up the identified gap in literature while concerning the Sri Lankan undergraduates and their mobile commerce usage when it comes to the Sri Lankan context. Undergraduates in Sri Lanka are in the highest place among digitally literate community, so that conducting a study on their usage on mobile commerce is very significant for the economy, policy makers, decision makers, and academia as well.

Research Objectives

- To identify factors that influence on usage of M-commerce among Sri Lankan undergraduates.
- To identify relationship between identified factors and usage of M-commerce by Sri Lankan undergraduates

Methodology

Conceptual Framework of the Study.

Many researchers have created models in line with the TAM of Davis to carry out their studies preferably. The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) of (Gitau & Nzuki, 2014) is selected to operationalize this study.

Figure 1. Conceptual framework

Hypotheses

H1: Perceived enjoyment is positively related to m-commerce usage among undergraduates.

H2: Perceived ease of use is positively related to m-commerce usage among undergraduates.

H3: Perceived usefulness is positively related to m-commerce usage among undergraduates.

H4: Social influence is positively related to m-commerce usage among undergraduates.

H5: Perceived security risk is negatively related to m-commerce usage among undergraduates.

Design of the Study

This study is a quantitative cross sectional empirical research approach.

Population and Sample

Population of the study consists about 12000 students who are the undergraduates at the University of Sri Jayewardenepura. As it is needed to focus the attention on undergraduates, the study was limited to Faculty of Management Studies and Commerce due to financial and time constrains. It has twelve departments, whereby cluster sample technique was used to select the sample. Sample size is calculated by ex-ante power analyses. According to ex ante power analysis, the required sample size is 91.

Operationalization

In the operationalization, each construct will be measured by using the questionnaire items in the previous research.

Data Analysis Methods and Tools

After collecting the data by distributing the online questionnaire, most critical part is to analyse the collected data. Data were analysed through descriptive analysis, validity and reliability testing and finally, hypotheses testing using SmartPLS 3 software.

Results and Discussion

Descriptive Data analysis

The population features of study participants the majority of final year female usage of M-commerce, 60% and 40%. The respondents belong to four years of study and they are Year 1, Year 2, Year 3, Year 4 respondents. 11, 13, 14 and 62 out of 100 are the number of respondents respectively. The percentages are 11%, 13%, 14% and 62% respectively. The year 4 respondents consist of 62%. There may be practical limitation that collects data from year 1, 2, and 3.

Reliability and Validity Analysis

All the items loadings, all Cronbach's Alpha and Composite reliability values are greater than 0.7 as suggested by Hair et al. (2011) and thus the indicator reliability and internal consistency was established (Hair et al., 2011).

As suggested by Hair et al. (2011), all the AVE values are greater than 0.5 and thus Convergent validity was demonstrated (Hair et al., 2011).

None of the constructs' cross-correlations exceeded the respective square root of each construct's AVE, thus discriminant validity was demonstrated.

Hypothesis Testing

Perceived ease of use was found to have significant 0.240 Positive effects on m-commerce usage ($P < 0.01$, 0.011).

Perceived enjoyment (0.106) was found to have positive effects on m-commerce usage among Sri Lankan undergraduates ($P < 0.01$, 0.411).

Perceived usefulness (0.148) was found to have positive effects on m-commerce usage ($P < 0.01$, 0.141).

Perceived security risk (0.090) was found to have negative effects on m-commerce usage ($P < 0.01$, 0.302).

Social influence was found to have significant 0.314 Positive effects on m-commerce usage ($P < 0.01$, 0.004) respectively.

Conclusion

The main findings were as follows.

Table 1: Summary of the Hypotheses Testing

Hypotheses	Path	Path	T statistics	P-value	Decision
H1	Perceived Ease of Use → Mobile Commerce Usage	0.240	2.555	0.011	Supported
H2	Perceived Enjoyment → Mobile Commerce Usage	0.106	0.823	0.411	Not supported
H3	Perceived Usefulness → Mobile Commerce Usage	0.148	1.476	0.141	Not supported
H4	Perceived Security Risk → Mobile Commerce Usage	0.090	1.033	0.302	Not Supported
H5	Social Influence → Mobile Commerce Usage	0.314	2.907	0.004	Supported

Implications

This research leads both theory and reality. In theoretical view, a greater interpretation of the factors that affect students' influence to use mobile commerce are offered by the conceptual model tested in the context of Sri Lanka. Although many studies can be found regarding mobile commerce usage among undergraduates of Faculty of Management Studies and Commerce at the University of Sri Jayewardenepura, no study can be found on the factors influencing M-commerce usage among them. Furthermore, m-commerce users also can get idea about the factors that influence on usage of M-commerce and relationship between identified factors and usage of M-commerce. Hence, they can make their decisions relating to m-commerce, using the findings of this study as they want. Students use m-commerce as that can save lot of time as well quote a cost benefit for the banks.

Limitations

Limitations of this study are as follows,

- The study focused on the Mobile commerce influence factors and usage among Sri Lankan undergraduates' context. To have a better understanding of the factors influencing usage on mobile commerce in Sri Lanka, it is important to focus on all other Universities of the country. There are 15 Universities which are listed under the University Grants Commission in Sri Lanka and it is imperative to understand the status in other universities as well.
- Management undergraduates were considered the respondents of the study as the study focused on undergraduate. However, to get a better understanding of mobile commerce usage in university, study of Mobile commerce usage of other faculty undergraduates is also important. Apart from the undergraduates, the people who use are also users dealing with the Mobile commerce. Further, the limited number of respondents also was a limiting factor of the study.

Recommendations

- Continuously provide proper Mobile Commerce awareness to the undergraduates and enhance the confidence of using Mobile Commerce.
- Include facilities and technology that can improve awareness and usage of Mobile Commerce.
- Provide well supportive facilities and respond quickly to e-mail enquiries regarding e-commerce related problems.
- Develop Mobile Commerce web site and enable the understanding related with m-commerce system.

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